

New records of Coleoptera from Lagodekhi Protected Areas, with new records for Georgia (Sakartvelo)

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Abstract

During this survey, 195 species of coleopterans have been recorded from the Lagodekhi Protected Areas (LPA). Thirty families are recorded for the first time from this area, of which Rhysodidae, Sphindidae and Thymalidae are new for Georgia. One hundred fifty-seven species are new to LPA and 66 of them are new country records.

Key words

Beetles, South Caucasus, Faunistics, Biodiversity Inventory

Introduction

The Lagodekhi Natural Reserve was established in 1912 (thanks to the efforts of the Polish forester and naturalist Ludwik Młokosiewicz (Chodubski 1982)), and is located in the extreme north-eastern part of Georgia (southern slopes of the Caucasus Mountains) with a range of altitudes from 590 to 3500 m above sea level. The Lagodekhi Protected Areas (LPA) include the Lagodekhi Natural Reserve (19,749 ha) and a Managed Reserve (4702 ha) (APA 2016). The LPA keeps one of the world's best-preserved primeval deciduous forest habitats (Fig. 1A). The first summarized paper about the insect diversity of Lagodekhi Natural Reserve was given by Kobakhidze (1956), listing 632 insect taxa (Japoshvili et al. 2022). A very recent update about the insect diversity of LPA provides 1790 species records for LPA (Mumladze et al. 2017; Japoshvili 2017, 2022; Japoshvili et al. 2022). This

makes the LPA the best studied protected area (by means of insect diversity) in the Caucasus Region. However, the true diversity of insect species in LPA is still far from being fully inventoried. For instance, materials collected in 2014 revealed 313 new species records for the family Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) for the LPA, including 209 new country records (Riedel et al. 2018). The coleopteran insects of LPA are relatively well known thanks to the old works by a number of authors (Chantladze 2000; Jambazishvili 2000; Cholokava et al. 2002; Javelidze et al. 2002; Merkviladze and Kvavadze 2002; Reck and Chaladze 2004; Cholokava 2008). However, Coleoptera, which is one of the most speciose orders of insects, is also supposedly represented by many more species in LPA than we know today. A recent work by Gul Aslan et al. (2017) who studied malaise trap material of leaf beetles (Chrysomelidae) collected in 2014, reported 48 species with 14 new country records. Here we

provide inventory data for a number of different families of Coleoptera, collected within the same malaise trap program mentioned above, and supplemented by other materials collected in recent years.

Materials and methods

The materials represented in the present article were collected by the first author using malaise traps (MT) operating in LNP during the entire growing season from April to November of 2014. However, at high altitudes (H5, H6 – see below), collecting began later (5 May 2014; alpine 23 May 2014) and was completed earlier (6 October 2014), due to climate conditions at higher altitudes. MTs (Fig. 1B) were placed at the following sites: H1: low-altitude forest, 666 m above sea level (a.s.l.) (N41.852483, E46.287767); H2: mid-altitude forest, 847 m a.s.l. (N41.854183, E46.292733); H3: high-altitude forest, 1351 m a.s.l. (N41.871467, E46.311533); H4: subalpine forest, 1841 m a.s.l. (N41.882733, E46.32185); H5: subalpine meadow and scrubland, 2230 m a.s.l. (N41.89805, E46.333883); H6: alpine zone, 2559 m a.s.l. (N41.906183, E46.3334). Before being sorted, samples were collected every 10 (\pm 2) days and kept in 96% ethanol. Additionally, 12-funnel traps (FT hereafter), from 1 May to 5 August 2014, and Moericke traps (yellow pan traps; hereafter - PT), from 1 May to 14 June 2014, have been used to supplement the MT collection (Fig. 1C). FTs and PTs were set up in the same localities as MTs. Finally, our material also contains data obtained using occasional hand collection (HC hereafter) during the various field research campaigns in LPA during the last decade. In such cases, geographic coordinates are given under each of the species listed below.

The following authors have helped to identify materials: S. Mazur (Histeridae), J. Borowski (Ptinidae), W.H. Rucker and R. Plewa (Latridiidae), A. Lasoń (Nitidulidae), A. Melke (Staphylinidae), R. Królik (Ciidae and Buprestidae), M. Wanat (Curculionidae (without Scolytinae)), J. Mertlik and G. Platia (Elateridae), and T. Gazurek (various taxa). The rest of the material was identified by the authors. All new records for LPAs are marked with one asterisk (*) and new country records with double asterisks (**). New country records were verified mainly based on the Catalogue of Palearctic Coleoptera (Löbl and Smetana 2006, 2007, 2011, 2013; Löbl and Löbl 2015, 2016, 2017; Danilevsky 2020; Iwan and Löbl 2020). In cases when we were not able to find an original source for the Georgian distribution of a particular taxon with no later confirmation, we did not take into consideration such records. The voucher materials are placed in the author's collections. The abbreviated names of the collectors are as follows: George Japoshvili – GJ; Radosław Plewa – RP; Jacek Hilszczański – JH; Jerzy Borowski – JB; Jacek Piętka – JP; Adam Byk – AB; Tomasz Jaworski – TJ; Krzysztof Łoś – KL. If the material was gathered by a group of people, we use the abbreviation IPT (IBL: Forest Research Institute (Instytut Badawczy Lenictwa) Polish Team). Material for correct terminology was checked according to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF 2022).

Results

In the species list given below, the information is provided in the following order: the number of specimens, sampling locality, sampling date, collection method, and collectors.

Order: Coleoptera

Family: Anthribidae*

Genus: *Dissoleucas* Jordan, 1925

Dissoleucas niveirostris (Fabricius, 1798)

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Platyrhinus* Clairville, 1798

Platyrhinus resinosus (Scopoli, 1763)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 29.05.2012; HC; leg: RP.

Genus: *Platystomos* Schneider, 1791

Platystomos albinus (Linnaeus, 1758)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 3.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Pseudeuparius* Jordan, 1914

Pseudeuparius sepicola (Fabricius, 1793)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 4.05.2014; HC; leg: RP.

Genus: *Choragus* Kirby, 1819

Choragus sheppardi (Kirby, 1819)

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H2; 5-14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Family: Biphylidae*

Genus: *Diplocoelus* Guérin-Ménéville, 1838

Diplocoelus humerosus Reitter, 1876

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 5-15.07.2014; MT.

Family: Buprestidae*

Genus: *Anthaxia* Eschscholtz, 1829

Anthaxia signaticollis Krynicki, 1832

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Coraeus* Laporte de Castelnau & Gory, 1839

Coraeus rubi (Linnaeus, 1767)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.23; 2.07.2011; HC; leg: JH.

Genus: *Dicerca* Eschscholtz, 1829

Dicerca chlorostigma Mannerheim, 1837

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.28; 30.05.2012; HC; leg: JH. 1 ind; H3; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 26.07-5.08.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.08.2014; MT.

Genus: *Chrysobothris* Eschscholtz, 1829

Chrysobothris affinis (Fabricius, 1794)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H5; 15-25.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Lamprodila* Motschulsky, 1860

Lamprodila rutilans (Fabricius, 1777)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 2.07.2011; HC; leg: JH.

Family: Carabidae

Genus: *Carabus* Linnaeus, 1758

Carabus septemcarinatus Motschulsky, 1840*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.28; 1.05.2014; HC; leg: KL.

Figure 1. A – Forest habitat near the main entrance of Lagodekhi National Park; B – Malaise trap in the mountain middle zone in a mixed mountain forest, with *Fagus orientalis* as a dominant tree species (Fageto-galiosum), 1351 m a.s.l.; C – Funnel and yellow pan traps, close to river along the road from main entrance to Lagodekhi National Park; D – Strongly decomposed beech snag; E – Snag of beech with emergence holes of *Rhaesus serricollis* (Motschulsky, 1838) (Cerambycidae); F – Bracket fungus with beetles of *Diaperis boleti* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Tenebrionidae).

C. staehlini Adams, 1817

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 17-23.06.2015; HC; leg: GJ.

Genus: *Tachyta* Kirby, 1837

Tachyta nana (Gyllenhal, 1810)

- GEORGIA • 3 inds; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 3.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Aegosoma* Audinet-Serville, 1832

Aegosoma scabricorne (Scopoli, 1763)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; HC; leg: JH; 2 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB, JP.

Family: Cerambycidae

Genus: *Agapanthia* Audinet-Serville, 1835

Agapanthia lederi Ganglbauer, 1884*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H6; 25.06-5.07.2014; MT.

Genus: *Alosterna* tabacicolor (Degeer, 1775)

- Alosterna tabacicolor subvittata* Reitter, 1885*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- Genus:** *Anaglyptus* Mulsant, 1839
Anaglyptus simplicicornis Reitter, 1906*
 ■ GEORGIA • 2 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT. leg: IPT.
- Genus:** *Aromia* Audinet-Serville, 1834
Aromia moschata ambrosiaca Steven, 1809
 ■ GEORGIA • 7 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB, JP.
- Genus:** *Cerambyx* Linnaeus, 1758
Cerambyx cerdo acuminatus Motschulsky, 1853
 ■ GEORGIA • 4 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB, JP.
- Genus:** *Chlorophorus* Chevrolat, 1863
Chlorophorus varius (Müller, 1766)*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.23; 2.07.2011; HC; leg: JH.
- Genus:** *Clytus* Laicharting, 1784
Clytus schneideri Kiesenwetter, 1879*
 ■ GEORGIA • 3 inds; N41.85, E46.23; 2.07.2011; HC; leg: JH.
- Genus:** *Cortodera* Mulsant, 1863
Cortodera pumila Ganglbauer, 1882*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.23; 2.07.2011; leg: JH. 2 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT. 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 15-25.05.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Exocentrus* Dejean, 1835
Exocentrus adpersus Mulsant, 1846*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.07.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- Genus:** *Fallacia* Mulsant & Rey, 1863
Fallacia elegans (Faldermann, 1837)*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 12-23.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 15-25.05.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Leiopus* Audinet-Serville, 1835
Leiopus femoratus Fairmaire, 1859*
 ■ GEORGIA • 2 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- L. nebulosus caucasicus* Ganglbauer, 1887*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Leptura* Linnaeus, 1758
Leptura quadrifasciata lederi Ganglbauer, 1882*
 ■ GEORGIA • 2 inds; N41.85, E46.23; 2.07.2011; leg: JH; 1 ind; H1; 25.06-5.07.2014; MT. 4 inds; H1; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB, JP.
- Genus:** *Mesosa* Latreille, 1829
Mesosa curculionoides (Linnaeus, 1760)
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 15-27.09.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Morimus* Brullé, 1832
Morimus verecundus (Faldermann, 1836)*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; HC; leg: JH. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.08.2014; MT. 2 inds; H1; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB.
- Genus:** *Nathrius* Brethes, 1916
Nathrius brevipennis (Mulsant, 1839)*
 ■ GEORGIA • 2 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- Genus:** *Parachytus* Bates, 1884
Parachytus sexguttatus (Adams, 1817)
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H2; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 4 inds; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H4; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H6; 25.06-5.07.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Parmena* Dejean, 1821
Parmena pontocircassica Danilevsky et Miroshnikov, 1985*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB.
- Genus:** *Phymatodes* Mulsant, 1839
Phymatodes femoralis Ménétrés, 1832*
 ■ GEORGIA • 5 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- Genus:** *Prionus* Geoffroy, 1762
Prionus coriarius (Linnaeus, 1758)*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.23; 2.07.2011; HC; leg: JH.
- Genus:** *Rhagium* Fabricius, 1775
Rhagium fasciculatum Faldermann, 1837*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 2-12.04.2014; MT. 3 inds; H1; 12-23.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; H2; 12-23.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 3 inds; H2; 4.05.2014; MT. 5 inds; H2; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 2 inds; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 2 inds; H4; 5-15.05.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Rhaesus* Motschulsky, 1875
Rhaesus serricollis (Motschulsky, 1838)
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; dead on beech snag (Fig. 1D); leg: JH. 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 1.05.2014; dead on beech snag; HC; leg: RP. 8 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB, JP.
- Genus:** *Rosalia* Audinet-Serville, 1833
Rosalia alpina (Linnaeus, 1758)
 ■ GEORGIA • 2 inds; H3; 14.07-5.08.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 24.08.2011; HC; leg: GJ. 6 inds; H3; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB, JP.
- Genus:** *Rutpela* Nakane & Ohbayashi, 1957
Rutpela maculata manca (Schaufuss, 1863)*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Stenocorus* Geoffroy, 1762*
Stenocorus insitivus insitivus (Germar, 1824)
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.29; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: AB.
- Genus:** *Stenostola* Dejean, 1835
Stenostola ferrea (Schrank, 1776)*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 12-23.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H2; 4.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H2; 5-15.05.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Stictoleptura* Casey, 1924
Stictoleptura tonsa (J. Daniel et K. Daniel, 1891)*
 ■ GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.23; 2.07.2011; leg: JH.

Genus: *Stromatium* Audinet-Serville, 1834*Stromatium unicolor* (Olivier, 1795)**

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB.

Genus: *Trichoferus* Wollaston, 1854*Trichoferus campestris* (Faldermann, 1835)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT. leg: IPT.

Genus: *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860*Xylotrechus arvicola* (Olivier, 1795)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

X. rusticus (Linnaeus, 1758)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.85, E46.23; 2.07.2011; HC; leg: JH.

Family: Cerylonidae***Genus:** *Cerylon* Latreille, 1802*Cerylon ferrugineum* Stephens, 1830**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 2 inds; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Family: Ciidae***Genus:** *Cis* Latreille, 1797*Cis festivus* (Panzer, 1793)

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. leg: IPT.

C. fusciclavis Nyholm, (1953)**

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H2; 5-14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

C. rugulosus Mellié, 1849**

- GEORGIA • 3 inds; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 10 inds; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; HC; PT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.06.2014; MT.

C. tomentosus Mellié, 1849*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: AB.

Genus: *Octotemnus* Mellié, 1847*Octotemnus rugosopunctatus* Drogvalenko, 2002**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 5-14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Family: Cleridae***Genus:** *Opilo* Latreille, 1802*Opilo mollis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

- GEORGIA • 3 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Thanasimus* Latreille, 1806*Thanasimus formicarius* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; HC; PT. 1 ind; H3; 15-25.05.2014; MT.

- The species is enlisted in Georgian Biodiversity Database (Tarkhnishvili and Chaladze 2022), without indication of voucher deposition or locality data.

Genus: *Tillus* Olivier, 1790*Tillus elongatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) **

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Family: Coccinelidae**Genus:** *Chilocorus* Leach, 1815*Chilocorus renipustulatus* (Scriba, 1791)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.

Family: Corylophidae***Genus:** *Arthrolips* Wollaston, 1854*Arthrolips picea* (Comolli, 1837)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 12-23.04.2014; MT. 2 inds; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 6 inds; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 2 inds; H1; 15-27.09.2014; MT.

Family: Cucujidae***Genus:** *Laemophloeus* Dejean, 1835*Laemophloeus monilis* (Fabricius, 1787)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Pediacus* Shuckard, 1839*Pediacus dermestoides* (Fabricius, 1793)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 2-12.04.2014; MT. 2 inds; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Cucujus* Müller, 1764*Cucujus haematodes caucasicus* Motschulsky, 1845*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT.

Family: Curculionidae**Genus:** *Anisandrus* J.A. Ferrari, 1867*Anisandrus dispar* (Fabricius, 1793)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 2-12.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 3.05.2014; MT. 5 inds; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H4; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 10 inds; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.08.2014; MT.

Genus: *Hylesinus* J.C. Fabricius, 1802*Hylesinus varius* (Fabricius, 1775)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 3.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Magdalis* E.F. Germar, 1817*Magdalis fallax* Kirsch, 1878*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Phloeotribus* P.A. Latreille, 1797*Phloeotribus scarabaeoides* (Bernard, 1788)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Platypus* J.F.W. Herbst, 1793*Platypus cylindrus* (Fabricius, 1793)**

- GEORGIA • 9 inds; H2; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT. 8 inds; H2; 4-14.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT. 4 inds; H1; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 7 inds; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 25.06-5.07.2014; MT. 3 inds; H1; 5-15.07.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.07.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 26.07-5.08. 2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.08.2014; MT. 24 inds; H2; 15-25.08.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 4-14.09.2014; MT.

Genus: *Scolytus* E.L. Geoffroy, 1762*Scolytus intricatus* Ratzeburg, 1837

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Taphrorychus* W.J. Eichhoff, 1878

Taphrorychus bicolor (Herbst, 1794)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Trachodes* E.F.Germar, 1823

Trachodes hystrix Gyllenhal, 1836*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.08.2014; MT.

Genus: *Xyleborinus* E.Reitter, 1913

Xyleborinus saxesenii Ratzeburg, 1837**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT. leg: IPT.

Genus: *Xylechinus* F. Chapuis, 1869

Xylechinus pilosus (Ratzeburg, 1837)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.07.2014; MT.

Genus: *Xylosandrus* E. Reitter, 1913

Xylosandrus germanus (Blandford, 1894)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H2; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT. 5 inds; H1; 5-15.07.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.08.2014; MT.

Family: Dasytidae

Genus: *Dasytes* Paykull, 1799

Dasytes niger (Linnaeus, 1760)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H5; 5-15.05.2014; MT.

Family: Elateridae

Genus: *Ampedus* Dejean, 1833

Ampedus ochropterus Germar, 1844*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT. 3 inds; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT.

A. pomorum (Herbst, 1784)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H2; 4.05.2014; MT. 3 inds; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT. leg: IPT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 15-25.05.2014; MT.

A. sinuatus Germar, 1844*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

A. wachtangi Dolin, 1970*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Anostirus* C.G.Thomson, 1859

Anostirus castaneus (Linnaeus, 1758)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Brachygonus* du Buysson, 1912

Brachygonus cf. *frater* Wurst, 1995**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Cardiophorus* Eschscholtz, 1829

Cardiophorus kryzhanovskiy Dolin & Chantladze, 1980

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Denticollis* Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783

Denticollis parallelcollis (Aubé, 1850)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 3 inds; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Hypoganus* Kiesenwetter, 1858

Hypoganus stepanovi Denisova, 1948*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Lacon* Laporte, 1838

Lacon punctatus (Herbst, 1779)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; leg: JH.

Genus: *Melanotus* Eschscholtz, 1829

Melanotus castanipes (Paykull, 1800)*

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

M. villosus (Geoffroy, 1785)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4.05-14.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Procaerus* Reitter, 1905

Procaerus carinifrons (Desbrochers des Loges, 1875)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Family: Endomychidae*

Genus: *Symbiotes* Philip, 1956

Symbiotes gibberosus (Lucas, 1846)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 4-14.06.2014; MT.

Family: Erotylidae

Genus: *Dacne* Latreille, 1797

Dacne semirufula (Reitter, 1897)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.07.2014; MT. 4 inds; 17-21.07.2019; leg: JB, AB, JP.

Genus: *Lycoperdina* Latreille, 1807

Lycoperdina succincta (Linnaeus, 1767)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.

Genus: *Triplax* Herbst, 1793*

Triplax aenea (Schaller, 1783)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.

Triplax elongata Lacordaire, 1842**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; HC; leg: JH.

Triplax rufipes (Fabricius, 1787)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 11 inds; 17-21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB, JP.

Genus: *Tritoma* Fabricius, 1775

Tritoma bipustulata Fabricius, 1775

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT.

Family: Eucnemidae*

Genus: *Dromaeolus* Kiesenwetter, 1858

Dromaeolus barnabita (Villa et Villa, 1838)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Isorhipis* Boisduval & Lacordaire, 1835

Isorhipis nigriceps (Mannerheim, 1823)**

- GEORGIA • 14 inds; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 4 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2012; leg: RP. 6 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 3 inds; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 3 inds; H2; 4.05.2014; MT. 12 inds; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 6 inds; H2; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 5 inds; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 3 inds; H1; 15-25.05.2014;

MT. 1 ind; H3; 25.05–4.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 15–25.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Xylophilus* Mannerheim, 1823

Xylophilus leseigneuri Olexa, 1960**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Family: Geotrupidae

Genus: *Odonteus* Samouelle, 1819*

O. armiger (Scopoli, 1772)**

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; 15–25.05.2014; HC; leg: GJ. 1 ind; 25.05–4.06.2014; HC; leg: GJ.

Genus: *Geotrupes* Latreille, 1797

Geotrupes olgae (Olsoufieff, 1918)*

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; 17–21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB.

Family: Histeridae*

Genus: *Onthophilus* Leach, 1817

Onthophilus striatus (Forster, 1771)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Paromalus* Erichson, 1834

Paromalus flavicornis (Herbst, 1791)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Family: Laemophlaeidae*

Genus: *Laemophloeus* Dejean, 1835

Laemophloeus monilis (Fabricius, 1787)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4–14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Family: Latridiidae*

Genus: *Cartodere* C.G. Thomson, 1859

Cartodere nodifer (Westwood, 1839)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 15–25.08.2014; MT.

Genus: *Corticaria* Marsham, 1802

Corticaria alleni Johnson, 1974**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 5–14.07.2014; HC; FT.

Genus: *Corticarina* Reitter, 1880

Corticarina similata (Gyllenhal, 1827)*

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H3; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06–5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 2 inds; H2; 5–14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Enicmus* C.G. Thomson, 1859

Enicmus brevicornis (Mannerheim, 1844)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Enicmus rugosus (Herbst, 1793)

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 23.04–3.05.2014; MT. 2 inds; H1; 5–15.05.2014; MT. 13 inds; H1; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 3 inds; H2; 1.05–14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06–5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 24 inds; H2; 5–14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 4 inds; H3; 14.07–5.08.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Enicmus testaceus (Stephens, 1830)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 1.05–14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H2; 5–14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Latridius* Herbst, 1793

Latridius consimilis (Mannerheim, 1844)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 5–14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

L. hirtus Gyllenhal, 1827**

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 2 inds; H2; 5–14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 2 inds; H3; 14.07–5.08.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

L. minutus (Linnaeus, 1767)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 5–14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

L. porcatus (Herbst, 1793)**

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H2; 5–14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Melanophthalma* Motschoulsky, 1866

Melanophthalma taurica (Mannerheim, 1844)**

- GEORGIA • 3 inds; H1; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Stephostethus* LeConte, 1878

Stephostethus alternans (Mannerheim, 1844)**

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 23.04–3.05.2014; MT.

Stephostethus angusticollis (Gyllenhal, 1827)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 5–15.05.2014; MT.

Family: Leiodidae*

Genus: *Anisotoma* Panzer, 1797

Anisotoma humeralis (Fabricius, 1793)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 12–23.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 1.05–14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Nemadus* C.G. Thomson, 1867

Nemadus colonoides (Kraatz, 1851)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H4; 3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 5–15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15–25.05.2014; MT. 3 inds; H3; 25.05–4.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 4–14.06.2014; MT. 2 inds; H1; 5–15.08.2014; MT. 2 inds; H1; 25.08–5.09.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5–15.09.2014; MT. 2 inds; H1; 15–27.09.2014; MT.

Family: Lucanidae

Genus: *Dorcus* Macleay, 1819

Dorcus parallelipedus (Linnaeus, 1758)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 26.07–5.08.2014; MT. 6 inds; 30.05.2012; HC; leg: AB. 6 inds; 17–21.07.2019; HC; leg: AB.

Genus: *Lucanus* Scopoli, 1763

Lucanus cervus (Linnaeus, 1758)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 25.06–5.07.2014; MT.

L. ibericus ibericus Motschulsky, 1845*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 24.08.2011; HC; leg: GJ. 17 inds; 17–21.07.2019; HC; leg: JB, AB, JP.

Genus: *Platycerus* Geoffroy, 1762

Platycerus perplexus Gusakov, 2003**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 2–12.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 12–23.04.2014; MT. 2 inds; H2; 12–23.04.2014; MT. 17 inds; H1; 3.05.2014; MT. 5 inds; H3; 9–15.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Sinodendron* Hellwig, 1792

Sinodendron cylindricum (Linnaeus, 1758)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 15–25.06.2014; MT.

Family: Lymexylidae*

Genus: *Hylecoetus* Latreille, 1806

Elateroides dermestoides (Linnaeus, 1761)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 15–25.05.2014; MT.

Family: Melandryidae***Genus:** *Melandrya* Fabricius, 1801*Melandrya caraboides* (Linnaeus, 1760)

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 3 inds; H1; 1-14.05.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 5 inds; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 2 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Melandrya rufipes Gebler, 1829**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1-14.05.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Orchesia* Latreille, 1807*Orchesia undulata* Kraatz, 1853

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 2 inds; H2; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Phloiortya* Stephens, 1832*Phloiortya tenuis* (Hampe, 1850)

- GEORGIA • 3 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Family: Mordellidae***Genus:** *Tomoxia* Costa, 1853*Tomoxia bucephala* Costa, 1854**

- GEORGIA • 6 inds; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 2 inds; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 2 inds; H1; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H2; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 25.06-5.07.2014; MT.

Family: Mycetophagidae***Genus:** *Eulagius* Motschulsky, 1845*Eulagius acernus* Motschulsky, 1845

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Litargus* Erichson, 1846*Litargus connexus* (Fourcroy, 1785)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 22-23.04.2014; MT. 6 inds; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 2 inds; H3; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.08.2014; MT.

Genus: *Mycetophagus* Hellwig, 1792*Mycetophagus ciscaucasicus* (Semenov, 1899)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

M. fulvicollis Fabricius, 1793

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H2; 12-23.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 30.05.2012; at night on snag; leg: JH.

M. quadripustulatus (Linnaeus, 1760)*

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28, 30.05.2012; at night on fungi bodies, leg: TJ.

Family: Nitidulidae***Genus:** *Cychnamus* Kugelann, 1794*Cychnamus luteus* (Fabricius, 1787)

- GEORGIA • 5 inds; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Cyllodes* Erichson, 1843**Cyllodes ater* (Fabricius, 1787)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; 17-21.07.2019, leg: AB, det. TG;

Genus: *Epuraea* Erichson, 1843*Epuraea aestiva* (Linnaeus, 1758)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.

E. melanocephala (Marsham, 1802)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 5 inds; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H1; 3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 5-14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

E. pallescens (Stephens, 1835)

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H2; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 2 inds; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 5 inds; H3; 5-14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Glischrochilus* Reitter, 1873*Glischrochilus grandis* (Tournier, 1872)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 3.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Ipidia* Erichson, 1843*Ipidia sexguttata* (Sahlberg, 1834)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 5-14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Soronia* Erichson, 1843*Soronia grisea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 5-14.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Family: Oedemeridae***Genus:** *Ischnomera* Stephens, 1832*Ischnomera coerulea* (Linnaeus, 1758)

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Family: Ptinidae***Genus:** *Caenocara* C.G.Thomson, 1859*Caenocara affine* (Sturm, 1837)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 5-15.07.2014; MT.

C. subglobosum (Mulsant & Rey, 1864)**

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 5-15.07.2014; MT.

Genus: *Hedobia* Dejean, 1821*Hedobia pubescens* (Olivier, 1790)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 2-12.04.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Hemicoelus* LeConte, 1861*Hemicoelus fulvicornis* (Sturm, 1837)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT.

Genus: *Hyperisus* Mulsant & Rey, 1863*Hyperisus plumbeum* (Illiger, 1801)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Plumilus* White, 1974*Plumilus grandicollis* (Ménétriés, 1832)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Ptinomorphus* Mulsant & Rey, 1868*Ptinomorphus rosti* (Pic, 1896)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H3; 14.06-5.07.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Ptinus* Linnaeus, 1767*Ptinus bififormis* Reitter, 1880

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

- P. swaneticus* Reitter, 1906
- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Xestobium* Motschulsky, 1845
- Xestobium rufovillosum* (De Geer, 1774)**
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 5-15.05.2014; MT.
- Family: Pyrochroidae***
- Genus:** *Pogonocerus* Fischer von Waldheim, 1812
- Pogonocerus thoracicus* Fischer von Waldheim, 1812**
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 2 ind; H3; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H5; 15-25.06.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Pyrochroa* Müller, 1764
- Pyrochroa coccinea* (Linnaeus, 1761)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT. 2 inds; H2; 5-15.05.2014; MT.
- Family: Rhysodidae****
- Genus:** *Omoglymmius* Ganglbauer, 1891
- Omoglymmius germari* (Ganglbauer, 1892)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- Family: Salpingidae***
- Genus:** *Salpingus* Illiger, 1801
- Salpingus caucasicus* Reitter, 1905**
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H1; 3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-27.09.2014; MT.
- Family: Scarabaeidae**
- Genus:** *Acanthobodilus* G. Dellacasa, 1983*
- Acanthobodilus immundus* (Creutzer, 1799)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Genus:** *Anomala* Samouelle, 1819*
- Anomala dubia abchasica* Motschulsky, 1854
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Genus:** *Cetonia* Fabricius, 1775*
- Cetonia aurata pallida* (Drury, 1773)
- GEORGIA • 10 inds; 24.08.2011; HC; leg: GJ. 1 ind; H3; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 7 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Genus:** *Euoniticellus* Janssens, 1953*
- Euoniticellus fulvus* (Goeze, 1777)
- GEORGIA • 2 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Genus:** *Maladera* Mulsant & Rey, 1871
- Maladera castanea* (Arrow, 1913)**
- GEORGIA • 3 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Maladera punctatissima* (Faldermann, 1835)
- GEORGIA • 2 inds; H1; 15-25.05.2014; HC; leg: GJ. 2 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Genus:** *Onthophagus* Latreille, 1802*
- Onthophagus coenobita* (Herbst, 1783)
- GEORGIA • 4 inds; N41.84, E46.27; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Onthophagus taurus* (Schreber, 1759)
- GEORGIA • 2 inds; N41.84, E46.27; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Genus:** *Oryctes* Hellwig, 1798*
- Oryctes nasicornis latipennis* Motschulsky, 1845
- GEORGIA • 3 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: JB, AB.
- Genus:** *Polyphylla* Harris, 1841*
- Polyphylla fullo* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- GEORGIA • 2 inds; 24.08.2011; HC; leg: GJ.
- Polyphylla olivieri* (Laporte, 1840)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 41.84, 46.27; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Genus:** *Protaetia* Burmeister, 1842
- Protaetia affinis pseudospeciosa* (Medvedev, 1964)*
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 41.84, 46.27; 17-21.07.2019; leg: JB.
- Protaetia speciosa speciosa* (Adams, 1817)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 41.84, 46.27; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.
- Family: Silvanidae***
- Genus:** *Uleiota* Latreille, 1797
- Uleiota planatus* (Linnaeus, 1761)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT. 1 ind; H1; 5-14.09.2014; MT.
- Family: Sphindidae****
- Genus:** *Aspidiphorus* Dejean, 1821
- Aspidiphorus lareyniei* Jacquelin du Val, 1859
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 5-15.07.2014; MT.
- A. orbiculatus* (Gyllenhal, 1808)
- GEORGIA • 3 inds; H2; 4-14.06.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.07.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 25.08-5.09.2014; MT.
- Family: Staphylinidae**
- Genus:** *Gyrophaena* Mannerheim, 1831
- Gyrophaena fasciata* (Marsham, 1802)*
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT.
- Genus:** *Lordithon* C.G.Thomson, 1859
- Lordithon trinotatus* (Erichson, 1839)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 25.05-4.06.2014; MT.
- Previously recorded by Japoshvili and Khachikov (2020).
- Family: Tenebrionidae**
- Genus:** *Corticeus* Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783
- Corticeus unicolor* Piller et Mitterpacher, 1783
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 1.05-14.06.2014; PT; leg: IPT.
- C. bicolor* (Olivier, 1790)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- C. suberis* (Lucas, 1864)*
- GEORGIA • 2 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- Genus:** *Cryphaeus* Klug, 1833
- Cryphaeus cornutus* (Fisher von Waldheim, 1823)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.
- Genus:** *Diaclina* Jacquelin du Val, 1861
- Diaclina testudinea* (Piller et Mitterpacher, 1783)
- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; leg: JH.

Genus: *Diaperis* Geoffroy, 1762

Diaperis boleti (Linnaeus, 1758)**

- GEORGIA • 65 inds; 30.05.2012; at night on fungi (Fig. 1F); HC; leg: TJ.

Genus: *Lagria* Fabricius, 1775

Lagria hirta (Linnaeus, 1758)*

- GEORGIA • 3 inds; H1; 15-25.06.2014; MT. 3 inds; H1; 5-14.09.2014; MT.

Genus: *Metaclisa* Jacquelin du Val, 1861

Metaclisa azurea (Waltl, 1838)

- GEORGIA • 14 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: JB, AB, JP.

Genus: *Neatus* LeConte, 1862*

Neatus subaequalis Reitter, 1920**

- GEORGIA • 8 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: JB, AB, JP.

Genus: *Neomida* Latreille, 1829

Neomida quadricornis (Motschulsky, 1873)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: JB.

Genus: *Platydemia* Laporte & Brullé, 1831

Platydemia tristis Laporte & Brullé, 1831

- GEORGIA • 6 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: JB, AB, JP.

Family: Throscidae**

Genus: *Aulonothroscus* Horn, 1890

Aulonothroscus brevicollis (Bonvouloir, 1859)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 15-25.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H3; 4-14.09.2014; MT.

Genus: *Trixagus* Kugelann, 1794

Trixagus dermestoides (Linnaeus, 1767)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT.

Family: Thymalidae**

Genus: *Thymalus* Latreille, 1802

Thymalus aubei Léveillé, 1877

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 17-21.07.2019; leg: AB.

Family: Trogossitidae*

Genus: *Nemozoma* Latreille, 1804

Nemozoma cornutum Sturm, 1826**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 1.05.2014; leg: RP. 3 inds; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Genus: *Tenebroides* Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783

Tenebroides mauritanicus (Linnaeus, 1758)**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; H3; 4-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

- The species is enlisted in Georgian Biodiversity Database (Tarkhnishvili and Chaladze 2022), without indication of voucher deposition or locality data.

Family: Zopheridae*

Genus: *Bitoma* Herbst, 1793

Bitoma crenata (Fabricius, 1775)

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; leg: JH; 1 ind; H1; 23.04-3.05.2014; MT. 1 ind; H1; 5-15.05.2014; MT.

Genus: *Colydium* Fabricius, 1793

Colydium filiforme Fabricius, 1793

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; HC; leg: JH.

Genus: *Endophloeus* Dejean, 1834

Endophloeus exculptus Germar, 1847

- GEORGIA • 8 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; leg: JH. 4 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; leg: RP.

Genus: *Pycnomerus* Erichson, 1842

Pycnomerus terebrans (Oliver, 1790)**

- GEORGIA • 6 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; leg: JH; 1 ind; N41.84, E46.28; 1.05.2014; leg: RP.

Genus: *Synchita* Hellwig, 1792

Synchita mediolanensis Villa et Villa, 1833**

- GEORGIA • 1 ind; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; HC; leg: JH.

Synchita separanda (Reitter, 1882)**

- GEORGIA • 2 inds; N41.84, E46.28; 30.04.2014; at night on snag; leg: JH.

Synchita undata (Guérin-Méneville, 1844)**

- GEORGIA • 3 inds; H3; 1.05-14.06.2014; FT; leg: IPT.

Summary

During this survey, 195 species of coleopterans, belonging to 42 families and 172 genera, have been recorded from Lagodekhi Protected Areas. Thirty families are recorded for the first time from the studied area, three of which, Rhysodidae, Sphindidae, and Thymalidae, are new family records for Georgia. One hundred fifty-seven species are new to LPA and 66 of them are new country records. Given the high landscape and habitat diversity of LNP and Georgia, this study can be considered as a snapshot of coleopteran diversity even for LNP. Thus, it can be expected that further research will yield many new species for LNP and Georgia as a whole.

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დასკვნა

ნაშრომში წარმოდგენილია ხეშეფრთიანების კვლევის შედეგები ლაგოდეხის დაცული ტერიტორიებიდან. შეგროვებულ იქნა 42 ოჯახის 195 სახეობა, რომლებიც 172 გვარში არიან გადანაწილებული. 30 ოჯახი და 157 სახეობის

ხოჭო საკვლევი ტერიტორიისათვის პირველად აღრიცხული, რომელთაგანაც 3 ოჯახი Rhysodidae, Sphindidae და Thymalidae და 66 სახეობა ახალი საქართველოს ფაუნისათვის.

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